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Negative space and the issue of transformation in the process of composition in art.

An image must be transformed by contact with other images, as is color by contact with other colors. A blue is not the same beside a green, a yellow, a red. No art without transformation¹

Robert Bresson

Introduction

Drawing streams are a creative method whose concept was created on the margins of works on my last graphic series *Gravity*. Work on *Gravity* took place from 2015 to 2017 and was a very tedious and monotonous process that required hours, days, weeks of carving woodcut matrices. At the turn of 2016/17, sensing the decline and exhaustion of this woodcut project's formula, subconsciously, but more and more regularly, I began to revisit drawing. Sketches and drawings filled the void - the unknown, which grew in my mind gradually. My practice of constant drawing slowly began to encompass almost all manifestations of everyday life, progressively changing the way in which I perceived the world. I began to feel life itself in categories of perception expanded with aesthetical experience. This experience of the surrounding world through drawing became a central idea around which my work has grown since then. I was increasingly shying away from graphics, which resulted in the reconfiguration and later, the disintegration of my previous graphic workshop. What was left were pens, pencils, and sheets of scratched paper. Consciously, I decided to lock myself up in the world of drawing for some time; field of interest saw the crystallization of new problems and

¹ Robert Bresson "Notes On Cinematography", Urizen Books New York.

perceptions about artistic creativity, which I decided to explore. The basic and most intense stage of my work was a 1.5-month research trip to Japan and a stay at a visiting researcher at the Tokyo University of Arts in 2018, which took place thanks to the National Science Center in Cracow. The trip at the same time constituted an artistic residence, during which I performed creative work using the previously prepared method of drawing streams. Artistic material, consisting in a total of approximately 1,200 artworks, which were mainly drawings, was created at that time. This artistic work comprises an autonomous, open artistic series, which constitutes an implementation of the aforementioned method; it has become a tool for exploring issues which are my areas of interest, regarding the composition of an art series. The large range of artistic material realized causes that a detailed analysis in the article below is not possible. The planned public presentation in favorable gallery conditions will serve as a publication supplementing this study. The following text describes the main assumptions of the creative method which I used. It presents selected sources of inspiration, as well as a sketch concerning the issues I have considered during my creative work, i.e., negative space as well as the questions of transformation in the process of composing an artwork.

The drawing streams method.

The assumptions of this creative method that I used during my stay in Tokyo were relatively simple. They first and foremost consisted in creating a certain continuum. Drawings were created one by one, in sequences - the so-called streams or drawing beams with a linear structure - for as long as possible. Continuant work had its purpose, which was to create and maintain a high intensity of creative concentration, subject to stabilization only during long, uninterrupted work. The second (external) essential assumption of the method was the experimental and artistic process of perception (flowing) of reality, which was subject to drawing notation. Observation, a specific experience, a creative reaction to the surrounding reality formed an integral and a very important element of the applied creative method. The third and most important (internal) premise was to shift the attention in the creative process to awareness of the relationship between the following images, and thus, to an abstract layer of sorts, for the work in creation. Drawing creativity in the streams method was thus constructed as a chain process, in which each subsequent element

formed the answer/reaction to the previous one, and at the same time asked the question regarding the shape of the next one. Each subsequent drawing session comprised the answer to the previous one, etc. The result was to be a projected multi-element composition with features of open improvisation, which would eventually reveal its structure. The reality of a particular image in the cycle results from the triangle of mutual dependencies in the creative process: 1) restrictions of the medium I have used; 2) from the degree of synchronization with the observed reality; 3) from a specific sequence of images and the position of a particular drawing work in the envisaged universe of the work. During the project, I modified the assumptions and also drew from my imagination; that said, I consider this to be particularly difficult. However, I began cautious attempts in this area in the series of ink drawings.

The stream drawing method became a kind of self-propelled vehicle, as well as an exercise and game, the rate of which was intensification of the creative flow and discovering new areas of creativity. Regarding her creative work, Louise Bourgeois said “So this is it: How am I going to be self-operating all by myself? Well, I can do that if I can invent something that keeps me going.”² Although total independence in the creative work that Bourgeois postulates is debatable, the above quote points to the fact that it is extremely important for the artist to actively discover new paths and methods of action that will allow him to create and thus “move forward”. Sometimes these are inconspicuous and forgotten directions that unexpectedly open up new possibilities for the creator-wanderer. The stream method in combination with drawing, which is a very personal technique, resulted in intensive development of the visual dictionary. In night drawings it functioned as a form of introspection. However, it has above all become an ideal tool to consider the problem which concerns me, regarding the composition of a work of art, namely the issue of negative space, which I understand as a carrier of the transformation effect in visual arts.

Hokusai Manga

One of the first impulses that prompted me to use drawing streams

² Quoted after: How to Be an Artist, According to Louise Bourgeois, Karen Kedmy: “So this is it: How am I going to be self-operating all by myself? Well, I can do that if I can invent something that keeps me going.”
<https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-artist-louise-bourgeois> (accessed on 13/08/2018)

method was my contact with the works of Katsushika Hokusai (1760 - 1849), and in particular the sketches of this artist, published in the 15-volume work entitled *Manga*. Hokusai made his debut as a designer by illustrating book novels, and despite the fact that he quickly gained great recognition as the author of multi-colored, technically complicated woodcuts, he did not give up this form of artistic activity and to the end of his life used the artistic possibilities offered by popular book publications. *Manga* is one of the many woodcut books created by him³, printed in a characteristic, cut color version⁴. The first volume was published in 1815, when Hokusai was 55 years old. The last three volumes were published posthumously, two of them as prints of previously unpublished sketches. Authorship of the third is questioned. James Michener defines the creative assumptions of *Manga* as a collection of casual sketches, comics, drawn things as they are⁵. Literally, the word manga means: stubborn drawings, irresponsible images, unlimited, free, improvised images, etc. Initially, Hokusai planned to publish *Manga* as a drawing book, however, he gave up this idea and it was published without text - as a collection of casual, unrelated sketches⁶, provided only with introductory words. *Manga* is a collection of sketches without a central idea, forming a free record of the various manifestations of life in Japan at that time. This lack of ideology, randomness, variability, chaoticism are features that constitute the axis of the applied creative method. Successive performances deny the former, ephemeral or brutally turn them into nothingness. The self-destructive,

³ Other woodcut books by Katsushika Hokusai are, e.g., *Mountains over Mountains* 3 volumes, *Random Drawings* 1 tom., *Images of Nature* 1 volume, *Illustrated Book of Domestic Manners* 3 volumes, *Lives of Courtesans at Itako* 1 volume, *Dance Instruction Manual* 1 volume, *Pictures Drawn in One Stroke* 1 volume, *Popular Designs of Comb and Tobacco Pipes* 3 volumes, *Drawing in Three Ways* 1 volume, etc. The listed items can be viewed at: <http://www.hokusai-katsushika.org/manga--books.html> (accessed on 31/08/2018)

⁴ *Hokusai Manga* is printed in three colors: black (sumi ink), gray (diluted sumi ink), and in light red, so-called *Beni* – it is a pigment obtained from *carthamus tinctorius* flowers. Such a color scheme is often found in low budget ukiyo - e publications. More information about pigments used in the Japanese woodcut is included in: Hirano, Chie “Kiyonaga: A Study of His Life and Works”, Published by Harvard for the Boston Museum of Fine Arts 1939 (note of the author A.W.)

⁵ James A. Michener, *The Hokusai Sketchbooks, Selections from the Manga* p. 11, ed. Charles E. Tuttle Company, 1989

⁶ Quoted after *The Floating World of Hokusai*: BBC Radio 4, broadcast 10:30am (UTC) 30 Aug 2012 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hokusai_Manga (accessed on 1/IX/2018)

chaotic and capricious nature of this work's composition is a shocking and highly inspirational phenomenon. What exactly is the topic of *Manga*? - the answer is - everything. So, we are dealing with an attempt to create a masterful total work. Hokusai - an old man, crazy about drawing, once again takes us on a journey through his energetic, unrestrained creative madness.

Katsushika Hokusai was considered one of the greatest Japanese draftsmen of his era, but few original drawings have survived until today. In the process of printing and publishing of the Japanese woodcut Ukiyo-e the original sketches and drawings created on thin bamboo paper (hanshi) were destroyed during the engraving of matrices.⁷ Thus, it is not certain how detailed the drawings were compared to woodcuts and to what extent they were transformed or improved by the master engravers and assistants. It seems likely that the layout of elements on the page could have been partially changed and sorted by the publisher as well.⁸ *Manga* is a work of color, which probably also significantly influenced the form of final graphic images. Interesting associations between the preserved drawings of Hokusai and the printing work are described by Theodore Bowie in the book *The Drawing of Hokusai*⁹. In the case of *Manga*, as in the whole ukiyo-e woodcut, we are dealing with a characteristic stratification in which the final form of the work, despite it imitating the lightness of the original drawing with a brush, is in fact a sophisticated graphic image. Awareness of this fact sends the insightful recipient back to attempts of reconstruction of the artist's original drawing vision in the mind.

Manga images are uneven in artistic terms - to the extent that they escape the criteria of unambiguous evaluation. A characteristic feature of Hokusai's creativity is constant forward movement, escape. Insatiability, struggling with own imperfections, deepening existential anxiety is the main drama and driving force behind his work. On his deathbed, Hokusai said: "If heaven could only grant me ten more years! Only five more, and I would have become a real painter"¹⁰ During his colorful and extremely productive

⁷ During the production of a graphic print in the traditional Japanese woodcut technique, the original engraving sketch drawn by the artist is glued directly on the woodcut board with rice glue; this is followed by the paper being mechanically removed from the board in such a way that the ink drawn on the sketch remains on the board - then the woodcut block is engraved, and later subject to a further process of making prints - copies on paper. The original drawing or design is destroyed during the creation of a woodcut matrix. (note of the author A.W.)

⁸ Author's hypothesis

⁹ Theodore Bowie, *The Drawings of Hokusai*, Indiana University Press. 1964

¹⁰ James A. Michener *The Hokusai Sketchbooks – Selections from The Manga*,

life Hokusai composed about 40,000 - 50,000 thousand woodcut images¹¹.

Happy dance (Yakko-odori)

The creative process with which we are dealing in *Manga* bears signs of creative thinking, brainstorming or divergent production¹². One of the interesting leitmotifs in the work of Hokusai is a multiplied character study. An example of this type of imaging on the pages of *Manga* is an illustration titled: *Happy dance*¹³. Multiple representation of the same character in the compositional field comprised the artist's constant creative practice¹⁴. *Happy dance* is one of the most perfect paintings of this type which carries a suggestive artistic effect, resulting from placing various phases of movement side by side. The theme of dance is an element that defines the space of a multi-element composition, within which we can mentally travel between individual elements, finding infinitely many ways in which the presented figure moves - dances. This type of presentation uses the phenomenon of discontinuities between individual components. It also provokes the recipient to interact and actively interpret the presented sequence - it creates the effect of mental inbetweening¹⁵ in the process of the work's reception. In the case of *Yakko - odori*, the effect of completing the missing image is also a multifaceted process and gives rise to the never-ending interactive interpretations of this presentation, circular in its nature. The multiplication of characters in *Happy dance* is the result of Hokusai's practice of a frantic study of characters, but it also acquires the dimension of a significant means of expression that widens the work's perception.

In 2017, personally inspired by *Hokusai Manga*, and in particular

Charles E. Tuttle Company, Inc. First Edition 1989

¹¹ Theodore Bowie, *The Drawings of Hokusai*, Indiana University Press. 1964, p. 21

¹² J.P Guilford. *Natura Inteligencji Człowieka*, PWN, Warszawa 1978, p. 412

¹³ Katsushika Hokusai , *Complete Hokusai – Manga Sketchbooks, Shogakukan*, Vol. 3, pp. 13-14

¹⁴ Theodore Bowie, *The Drawings of Hokusai*, Indiana University Press. 1964. p. 81

¹⁵ **Inbetweening** or **tweneing** is a key process in all types of , including **computer animation**. It is the process of generating intermediate frames between two images, called **key frames**, to give the appearance that the first image evolves smoothly into the second image. **Inbetweens** are the drawings which create the illusion of motion.

quoted after: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inbetweening>

Katsushika Hokusai, *Happy dance*, page from *Hokusai Manga vol. III*. Source: Michener, James A. (1958) *Hokusai Sketchbooks: Selections from the Manga*, Rutland, Vermont & Tokyo: Charles E. Tuttle Company.

an illustration of *Happy dance*, I created a series of small sketches depicting children. This aforementioned drawing cycle forms a transposition of this particular creative practice into my intimate reality. Drawings were collected in the form of a small book entitled: “Olek Manga” published in 2017 as a limited edition.

Flowing images in the work of Francis Bacon.

In the book by David Sylvester *Interview with Francis Bacon* the artist speaks about his method of work as follows: *I paint one image after another. Each one includes a suggestion of the next, and then: I see every picture in a variable way, and even in smoothly changing sequences. Therefore, it can be carried out from what is usually called figuration, to some far, distant region*¹⁶. Regarding flowing images, he adds: *I would like to paint entire rooms of pictures presenting different topics but treated as a cycle. I see rooms full of images that flow just like a slide. For days I can imagine rooms filled with paintings. Regardless of whether they will ever be made, I like what falls into my head, I do not know what it is, because it always disappears somewhere. Everyone hopes that I will paint a picture which will invalidate all others, a picture that concentrates everything on one canvas. In a series, one image reflects the other in a certain continuation. Sometimes they are better in a series than separately. Unfortunately, I have not yet been able to create an image that would sum up the experience of all previous ones. It seems that images arranged side by side can convey more*¹⁷ It is a commonly known fact that the artist is fascinated by film, Muybridge’s sequential photography from which he draws interesting conclusions regarding his own painting solutions. From the moment he painted *Three Studies for Figures at the Base of a Crucifixion*¹⁸, Bacon has consciously used sequences of images in his work. The most commonly used form of multi-image composition is the triptych. An interesting attempt to analyze the formula of the Triptych in Bacon’s work was made by Gilles Deleuze¹⁹. It is also worth noting that the triptych functions in Bacon’s art as if out of necessity - as an extreme formalization

¹⁶ David Sylvester *Rozmowy z Francisem Baconem. Brutalność Faktu*, ed. Zysk i S-ka Wydawnictwo. 1997, p. 21

¹⁷ David Sylvester *Rozmowy z Francisem Baconem. Brutalność Faktu*, ed. Zysk i S-ka Wydawnictwo. 1997, p. 22

¹⁸ Since 1944 (note of the author)

¹⁹ Gilles Deleuze, *Francis Bacon - the Logic of Sensation*, chapter Couples and Triptychs and Note: What is a Triptych, 1981

of the sequence of flowing images. Bacon is aware of the resonance and repercussion of images, and his art explores expressive possibilities offered by transformations of composition systems in the artistic series. The degree of the problem's complexity; multi-layeredness, often irrationality of dependence in Bacon's painting intensifies his art's expressiveness and puts this creator among the most outstanding painters who have taken up the motif of transformation in their work.

Pablo Picasso, the logic of change.

In the context of my reflections regarding the composition of a multi-component cycle, I would like to mention one made at the turn of 1945/46, the very well-known but still extremely interesting series of graphic works entitled *Le Taureau* (Taurus) by Pablo Picasso. It is a set of eleven consecutive prints made in the lithography technique. The proof method used by the artist²⁰, relies on subsequent modifications of the same object. Each subsequent graphic state of *Le Taureau* constitutes a special apogee of the creative process, preserved in the form of a print on paper. This creates the context of reception of this graphic cycle in a certain continuum and allows for "insight" into consecutive stages of work on the image. *Le Taureau* has a seemingly clear transformation vector - from a free, full drawing with a brush - to maximum simplification of the linear motif presented. Taking a detailed look at the abrupt changes, which the title *taurus* is subject to, we are confronted with the enigmatic, alogous nature of their transformation. Detailed solutions for the succession of images used by Picasso demonstrate an arbitrary dimension, belong to the secret of the artist's expression and do not undergo simple analysis or reconstruction. *Le Taureau* reveals the inscrutable, brutal face of Picasso's poetic logic, descending to the inside of the vision via his own path. The last, surprising chord of *Le Taureau* are two, small drawing boards in the form of casual sketch etudes (*Etudes de Taureaux, Feuille'd Etudes de Taureaux*), which comprise a continuation of the cycle in imaginary form, or concept drawings for (...) an already completed lithographic cycle. According to one of the critics *Le Taureau is a work in which Picasso first presented rules regarding the metamorphosis of form in a graphic medium*²¹. In fact,

²⁰ Picasso uses both the drawing reduction technique and also applies new elements that transform the work. (note of the author)

²¹ *Quoted after: The Lithographical Series Le Taureau - Form Metamorphosis: "Between DECEMBER 5, 1945 and JANUARY 17, 1946, Picasso created the lithographical series Le Taureau, in which he for the first time vividly*

all of Picasso's art is saturated with a brutal and unrestrained sense of transformation, introduced by the unique creative power of this artist²².

The poetic space “in between”.

The result of my artistic practice, as well as analysis and interpretation of selected artists' work, was a significant breakthrough in my understanding of the composition of a work in a moment, during which I realized the presence and meaning of an active space BETWEEN or at THE POINT OF CONTACT of two or more images in the compositional process. This space can be defined as a hidden, abstract layer in the composition structure of a work that has the potential to significantly condition its final shape. American poet Gertrude Stein illustrates this problem clearly:

Cordially yours.
Pause.
Cordially yours.²³

In the quoted short passage of the poem *Sacred Emily*, the gap between lines is clearly defined and accentuated by (...) another line. Such a procedure reveals and concretizes the existence of an empty space between (in this

demonstrated his principle of form metamorphosis in the medium of graphic printing (cf. Le taureau IV [OPP.45:020]). In all, he lithographed eleven versions of a bull figure in profile. The different representations reach from a naturalistically marked rendition of the motif in the first state, to an abstractly reduced sign in the eleventh and last state. Most commentators describe this as the development of the object from reproduction to archetype, i.e. through reduction the form develops from complicated to simple, from detail to summary shape, and from plasticity to linearity” (cf. Hirner 2001, 124-126). Source: database Online Picasso Project. Mallen, Enrique, ed. Online Picasso Project. Sam Houston State University. 1997-2018. <https://picasso.shsu.edu/index.php?view=BioCommSearch&page=1&Keywords=le+taureau&Commentary=&SearchStyle=Continuous&SearchBy=monthday&StartMonth=1&StartDay=1&StartYear=1881&EndMonth=12&EndDay=31&EndYear=1973&Sort=asc> (accessed on 30/08/2108)

- ²² More information about the Le Taureau cycle can be found in an interesting article: Irvinga Lavina titled “Picasso's Lithograph(s) ‘The Bull (s)’ and the History of Art in Reverse” https://publications.ias.edu/sites/default/files/Lavin_OP_ArtWithoutHistory_1987.pdf (accessed on 20/09/ 2018) note of the author
- ²³ Fragment of poem *Sacred Emily* by Gertrude Stein – from the collection: *Geography and Plays*, 1922

case identical) verse lines.

How can one define empty space in art? Essentially, visual arts use the term “negative space”, i.e., unpainted, empty space on the image – the so-called *non-figure*. It comprises a kind of supporting space, a background on which the figure is placed. In two dimensions, it is both the reverse and complement of the figure. An example imaging of this problem is the so-called Rubin’s vase.

In the presented diagram we are dealing with two complementary images. One of them is a vase (white), and the other is two faces facing each other (black). Depending on the focused attention, we are able to see either one or the other. It is very difficult, and in principle impossible to see two presentations at the same time. Therefore, we are dealing with a hierarchy in

which one of the images dominates over the other, while the other plays a subordinate role to the first. In the longer sequence of images that can symbolize a series of artworks, we are dealing with the following situation:

We see the alternating occurrence of black and white forms. If we were to define black shapes as a form, then we would be dealing with a cycle of identical images (heads) between which there would be negative space. And vice versa - assuming that white forms are a form - we have a series of identical vase images.

But negative space can also occur between two different images. The example diagram illustrates deformations that exist at the interface between negative space and various figures:

Rubin's vase is a symbolic and simplified demonstration of dependencies that take place on a two-colored plane, at a black shape – white shape junction. In practice, such dependence in art is much more complicated. Negative space also exists between any two painting objects with a more complex structure than a silhouette (e.g., shades of gray, color), and between three-dimensional or poetic objects. In this case, negative space becomes complicated, becoming the carrier of complex relationships occurring between two separate structural elements. This space between images can be described as another abstract image, implied at the interface of two separate representations. The nature of this type of image is dynamic and immaterial - measurable only through the induced sensation that arises during the work's reception. Negative space is therefore the carrier of an essential compositional element - a metaphorical internal image shaped at the junction of two performances.

Where cuckoo
vanishes -
an island.²⁴

The above poem by the Japanese poet Matsuo Basho comprises an example of the virtuoso use of negative space understood in such a way to create a poetic internal image. Matsuo Basho is one of the most perfect haiku Japanese poets. A legend has built up around his restless lifestyle, compulsive and week-long wanderings, during which his journals, as well as poetry were created.²⁵ The source of artistic movements in Basho's poetry are epiphanies, which are the result of a sublime naturalistic practice, a non-selective experience of everyday life. The quoted poem presents the image that takes place near the Inner Sea, on which the poet looks down from the top of Tekkai. In it, the artist uses a juxtaposition of consecutive pictures - the disappearing (in the fog) cuckoo and the emerging (in this place) (like a dream) of an island (Awaji)²⁶. The isolation and subtle implication of the consequences of two seemingly unrelated, contradictory images creates a resultant - complex, spatial poetic structure. The essence of the poem's emotions is a surprising, not explainable, logical dissonance taking place between two pictures placed next to each other.

Strictly defined formal rules, according to which haiku were created, control the aforementioned literary miniature's aesthetic shape, but also play a protective role against the degradation of poetic tissue²⁷. Minimalism, idiomatic to the poetry of haiku, plays a role that strengthens and extends the space of resonance of feeling, which emphasizes the contemplative nature of the aforementioned internal poetic structure.

In the quoted poem negative space occurs in two forms - the first - metaphorical, at the junction of two "images" and the other as a surrounding, meditative space of internal resonance.

²⁴ Quoted after: Basho *on love and Barley – Haiku of Basho* Translated by Lucien Stryk, Penguin Classics first published in 1985, p. 39

²⁵ See: *The Records of a Weather – exposed Skeleton, A Visit to the Kashima Shrine, The Narrow Road to the Deep North* (note of the author)

²⁶ Quoted after *Classic Haiku: An Anthology of Poems by Basho and His Followers*, translation: Asataro Miyamori, Dover Publications; Bilingual edition (November 2, 2011) p. 67

²⁷ I am referring to the perfect introduction to composition techniques used in haiku, with special emphasis on the poetry of Basho, by Nobuyuki Yuasa: Matsuo Basho *Narrow Road to Deep North and other Travel Sketches*, Penguin Books, first published in 1966.

MA

The Japanese culture includes an interesting concept regarding the functioning of space, the perception of which in Japanese culture exceeds the known three-dimensional model and is a phenomenon that occurs during the progressive experiencing of structural elements and breaks between them. Dilatations between elements are called *MA*. *MA: the natural distance between two or more things existing in a continuity or the space delineated by posts and screens (rooms) or the natural pause or interval between two or more phenomena occurring continuously*²⁸. *Ma* is stimulated by specific divisions, the physical distance between objects, but it also enters the time domain. *The dualistic approach of Ma to time and space has not only a semantic character - it reflects the fact that every experience of space is a process embedded in the structure of time, as well as every experience of time is embedded in the spatial structure*²⁹ *Ma* also means a substantial mental space, consciousness, a burdensome void, a space in which the spirit moves (Japanese: *kami*). “*Ma*” is not something that is created by compositional elements in themselves, but rather happens in the imagination of man who experiences these elements. Therefore, “*Ma*” can be defined as the space of experience, understood in terms of an interval³⁰. *Ma* is a discreet conception penetrating the Japanese culture, which depends on objective spatial relations within the work’s structure but also in an interesting way subjectivizes these dependencies by situating them in the space of experience³¹. Negative space interpreted in the

²⁸ Quoted after: Cellucci, Cristiana. (2015). *MA - SPACE/TIME*. STUDIO, Architecture and Urbanism magazine. 90-97.

²⁹ Quoted after an online article at www.kyotojournal.org, author: Gunter Nitschke *MA: Place, space, void* <https://kyotojournal.org/the-journal/culture-arts/ma-place-space-void/> (accessed on 5/08/2018)

³⁰ “*Ma*” - is a Japanese word meaning the negative space of reality in the broad sense of this word. (note of the author) (author’s translation) see The Japanese spatial concept is experienced progressively through intervals of spatial designation. In Japanese, *ma* the word for space suggests interval. It is best described as a consciousness of place, not in the sense of an enclosed three-dimensional entity, but rather the simultaneous awareness of form and non-form deriving from an intensification of vision. *Ma* is not something that is created by compositional elements; it is the thing that takes place in the imagination of the human who experiences these elements. Therefore *ma* can be defined as experiential place understood with emphasis on interval. Quoted after: *Ma – The Japanese Spatial Expression*

quoted after: <http://www.columbia.edu/itc/ealac/V3613/ma/> accessed on 29/08/2018

³¹ Compare: Gunter Nitschke *MA: Place, space, void*

category of a universal interval introduces a certain coherence regarding the reception of Japanese art. Its scope in the culture of the country of cherry blossoms is (was) much wider and it also refers to craft and other aspects of everyday life.

Akino Kondoh comics:

In 2018 I had the opportunity to visit the presentation of Akino Kondoh's work at the Mori Art Museum in Tokyo. Akino Kondoh is a Japanese visual artist who lives in New York³². He deals with drawing, painting, animated film, creates comics. Her work refers to the stylistics of manga - understood as a contemporary, Japanese popular comic. The artist refers to the medium of the comic and uses the aesthetics of a static image to create poetic narratives. The leitmotiv in the animated film *Kiya* is the Kamishibai picture theater³³. The main character, Eiko, the narrator, through revealing subsequent boards with pictures, introduces us to her story, which is a series of hypnotizing, oneiric images. The effect of a narrative image transformation also occurs in many other animated films of this artist. However, at the said exhibition, my special attention was drawn to an unusual form of video presentation, consisting in displaying consecutive static comic charts on the screen. The presented comic works are: *The Boy in the Cabinet* 2005 / 2018 3 min. 7 sec., *Rendezvous* 2005 / 2018 1 min. 58 sec., *The Bridge of Dreams* 2015 / 2018 5 min. 40 sec.³⁴ Clashes of stationary comic boards on the big screen, in time, built an unusual, hybrid space of the work's perception, much more interesting than the literal image of a smoothly animated image. The aforementioned presentation, being a combination of several methods for decoding the work, pointed to the multifariousness and interesting poetic potential that lies in the static picture presented in the form of a slideshow. She also shed a new light on the basic issue regarding the nature of the comic as a medium which produces a specific continuum in which the imagination of the recipient plays a significant role.

<https://kyotojournal.org/the-journal/culture-arts/ma-place-space-void/> (accessed on 5/08/2018)

³² Artist's website: www.akinokondoh.com (accessed on 26/09/2018)

³³紙芝居 *kami-shibai*. The so-called picture theater in which the story told by the narrator is accompanied by a presentation of static images presented in parallel with the story told in a small cardboard theater. Kamishibai was a poor form of street entertainment in Japan that attracted audiences, mainly children, prior to the development and widespread availability of television.

³⁴ <https://www.mori.art.museum/en/exhibitions/mamscreen008/index.html> (accessed on 25/08/2018)

The art cycles of Seiichihiro Miida

Authentic artistic creation, comprising an element that does not fit into this world, is always astonishing. In the case of my contact with the work of Seiichihiro Miida, the first reaction was an internal dissonance, combined with a tangible sensation of the mysterious logic and inexplicable coherence of his paintings. The following comments on the work of Seiichihiro Miida particularly concern the Little Story cycle (2014-2016), as well as the last (2016-2018) series of drawing notes. A supplementary article is also the interview I conducted with the artist during my stay in Tokyo.

Seiichihiro Miida is a very prolific artist. The abundance of his drawings, paintings, graphics and sculpture goes hand in hand with their diversity, variability, as well as atypical configurations of materials and artistic means used by their author. He creates from nature, memory or from imagination. The boundary between these realities in his art seems to be fluid. As he himself said, the main subject of his interest is the construction of new visual grammars. My attention was drawn to the artist's particular sensitivity regarding the area of transformation and construction of various tensions at the interface of painting, graphic and drawing techniques, as well as skillful manipulation of the variability of composition arrangements. Miida's drawing cycles consist of seemingly mismatched elements that do not exist independently to some extent. Only when subjected to a distanced view, juxtaposed into wider strings or non-linear structures, they obtain the dimension of poetic space in which the reception takes place on the basis of a "journey" between successive artifacts. The essence of Seiichihiro Miida's drawings lies not only in the constituent elements - pictures, but is of a structural nature and can be read more widely - in their combinations and in the suggestive possibility of making a mental jump between individual elements. Seiichihiro Miida's work is an artistic expression, shaped discontinuously into the likeness of language (sentential).³⁵ Individual transformations evoke the construction of a koan - a specific Buddhist formula disciplining a student who, through his paradoxical construction, evokes a vision of poetic character. Asked a question regarding *Ma* space, Seiichihiro Miida answered – *is only a substitute subject, I have no purpose in what I do, I just want to draw!*³⁶ This type of evasive answer can be a koan in itself. The perceptible existence of a specific resonance between images indicates this creator's intelligent and sensitive use of the

³⁵ Enrique Mallen, "The Visual Grammar of Pablo Picasso", Berkeley Insights in Linguistics and Semiotics, ed. Peter Lang, Publishing, New York. P. 34

³⁶ Vide: Aleksander Woźniak *Conversation with Seiichiro Miida*, 2018

transmissive character of negative space. The intensity and character of these transformations obtains the status of a full-fledged element of communication, and also subject to an intuitive compositional process. Miida's art is only seemingly figurative. Both images that depict (and thus evoke a certain kind of emotion), as well as combinations of specific tools and materials used play the role of markers and comprise a tool in a process which is difficult to grasp, but has its logic of constructing a reference frame defining the space of this artist's unique vision. Existence of this type of continuity and structural relationship between individual images underlies the internal coherence of his art.

This may lead to the question: What happened 6 years ago when Seichihiro Miida began drawing?

Negative space and transformation as a phenomenon subject to the process of composition in art

Negative space is a universal phenomenon, on many levels inscribed in the structure of a work of art. It accompanies form, penetrates it and descends into every detailed artistic structure. As such, it is subject to artistic shaping and composition. In the image plane, negative space appears as a background, the reverse of a figure. It also functions outside the defined image area in the form of an echo or spatial resonance. In a multi-element composition, its shape can determine the ratio of distance between elements of a piece of art, their size, etc. Transformation, or a complex transformation between two separate structural elements, may be treated as an abstract, a dynamic image "in between" characterized by specific emotional properties. In this type of complex cases, negative space comprises the dynamic shape of transformation space or coexistence of two separate structural elements, e.g., compositional elements in the image, two images (diptych) or a series of phantom, parallel images in a wider set of objects (series, cycle, set of works). Another form of negative space is a hidden general picture from which individual, fragmentary instances of the work are born. It performs the function of a puzzle, subject to intuitive decryption by the recipient of the work.

Transferring attention to the reality of negative space in the creative process is an appealing interpretation path. It can also form an

interesting point of view, as well as a discreet decision center from which the artist has a chance to influence the shape of the work created. Creation and harmonization of dynamic relationships in an artistic work, that *de facto* comprises the composition of a creation, is an extremely complicated issue, and free shaping of a work's composition is every artist's greatest achievement and ultimate goal . In search of the shape of the abstract space "in between", let us shy away from too far-reaching theorizing of this problem; we should rather work on pictures, including awareness of its existence in this process.

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